

Seagrass Bioregional Species Key:

6 Temperate Southern Oceans Bioregion

Species identification key including photo guide, global range maps, drawings, and flowers.

From:

SeagrassNet

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With ratings from:

IUCN Red List of Threatened Species

Seagrass Red List

*Bioregional Guide to the Seagrass Species of the World. 2025. F.T. Short.
Available on-line www.SeagrassNet.org.*

Pa

Posidonia australis

Bioregion

6

Key

- Leaves 40-60 cm
- Leaf tip rounded
- Rhizome robust, brush-like and fibrous
- Flowers emerge on a stem
- Monoecious

Flowering Parts

Photos from Gary Kendrick

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Pn *Posidonia sinuosa*

Bioregion
6

Justin McDonald

Key

- Leaves ribbon like, 140 cm
- Leaf tip rounded
- Leaf sheath membranous
- Flowers emerge at base
- Monoecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Pg

Posidonia angustifolia

Bioregion

6

Gary Kendrick

Key

- Leaves ribbon like, 80 cm
- Leaf tip rounded
- Rhizome robust, pale fibers
- Flowers emerge on a stem
- Monoecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Pf

Posidonia ostenfeldii

Bioregion

6

Key

- Leaves thick, round and up to 180 cm
- Leaf tip rounded
- Rhizome enclosed in fine pale fibers
- Flowers emerge on a stem
- Monoecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Gary Kendrick

Pd *Posidonia denhartogii*

Bioregion
6

Key

- Leaves biconvex 120 cm
- Leaf tip rounded
- Rhizome robust, pale fibers
- Flowers emerge on a stem
- Monoecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Aa *Amphibolis antarctica*

Bioregion
6

Key

- Wiry stems 1.5 m long
- Leaf crowns of 6-10 bidentate blades
- Strap-like leaf blades (5 cm) twisted

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

seedling

Ag *Amphibolis griffithii*

Bioregion
6

- Key
- Wiry stems 1.0 m long
 - Leaf crowns of 4-5 notched blades
 - Strap-like leaf blades (3-10 cm)

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

ian.umces.edu

Zo *Heterozostera polychlamys*

Bioregion
6

Key

- Squared leaf tip, shallow notch
- Wiry erect stems, not black
- Strap-like leaf blades (0.5-2.5 mm wide)
- Shoot 100 cm long

Lotte Horn

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Australia only

Z† *Heterozostera tasmanica*

Bioregion
6

- Key
- Rounded leaf tip, deeply notched
 - Wiry erect stems, not black
 - Strap-like leaf blades (35cm long)

Extinction Risk: Data Deficient

Australia only

Zr *Heterozostera nigricaulis*

Bioregion

6

Key

- Squared leaf tip, notched
- Wiry erect stems, black
- Shoot 100 cm long

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Zh *Heterozostera chilensis*

Bioregion

6

Extinction Risk: **Endangered**

Chile only

Rm *Ruppia maritima*

Bioregion
6

- Key
- Leaves flat and thin
 - Leaf tapers to tip
 - Leaves 4-22 cm long
 - Depth -1-20 m

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

male

Flowering Parts

female

fruit

Si *Syringodium isoetifolium*

Bioregion
6

Key

- Leaves cylindrical
- Leaf tips taper
- Leaves 7-30 cm long
- Dioecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

male

female

fruit

Tc *Thalassodendron ciliatum*

Bioregion
6

- Key
- Cluster of leaves on an erect stem
 - Leaves 10-40 cm
 - Sickle-shaped leaves with serrated tips
 - Rhizome woody
 - Dioecious
 - Leaves often have red cross-stripes

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

Tp *Thalassodendron pachyrhizum*

Bioregion
6

- Key
- Cluster of leaves on an erect stem
 - Leaves 10-15 cm, thin ribbons
 - Sickle-shaped leaves with serrated tips
 - Rhizome woody
 - Dioecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Australia only

Zc *Nanozostera muelleri*

Bioregion
6

Shaun Lee 2024

Tony Strazzari

- Key
- Round leaf tip deeply notched
 - Strap-like leaf blades (1-2 mm)
 - Leaves 10-60 cm long
 - Persistent leaf sheath
 - Monoecious
 - Previously known as *Zostera capricorni*

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

Rachel Hooks 2024

de Kock et al. 2016

female

Zp *Nanozostera capensis*

Bioregion
6

- Key
- Round indented leaf tip
 - Leaf with staggered cross veins
 - Strap-like leaf blades (0.5-2.5 mm)
 - Leaves 10-115 cm long
 - Persistent leaf sheath
 - Monoecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

Ha *Halophila australis*

Bioregion
6

Key

- Oval-shaped leaf pairs
- Leaves 2-7 cm long
- No leaf hairs
- Leaf margins smooth
- Dioecious
- Depth 0-10 m

Flowering Parts

Flowers unique on an erect stalk, female with 6 styles.

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Ho *Halophila ovalis*

Bioregion

6

Key

- Oval-shaped leaves
- Leaves 1-4 cm long
- No leaf hairs
- Leaf margins smooth
- Depth 0-10 m
- Dioecious

Flowering Parts

female

male

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Hd *Halophila decipiens*

Bioregion

6

Key

- Paddle-shaped leaves
- Leaf hairs on both sides
- Leaf margins serrated
- Leaves 1-4 cm long
- Monoecious
- Depth 0-30 m

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

male & female

fruit

Global Seagrass Species References

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